

Agile FAIR Data for Environment and Earth System Communities

EOSCPillar4EarthScience Virtual Research Environment

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1. Introduction

Earth Environment sciences & Geosciences require a large panel and volume of data from satellite, in-situ observations and climate models, that are managed and preserved separately in domain-dependent repositories of national or European infrastructures. As the data sources are widely distributed, it induces real difficulties to achieve inter-processing and integrated uses of the data for comprehensive studies at domain or cross-domain level.

In the context of the [EOSC-Pillar](#) project, the [Work Package 6](#) (*EOSC in action: Use cases and community-driven pilots*) delivers use cases to analyze different tools and services for the "FAIRisation" of data and services. Among them, the use case "[Agile FAIR Data for Environment and Earth System Communities](#)" aims at offering services to facilitate and speed up the access to the distributed data sources and provide a web-based processing environment for Data Science notebooks supporting the Pangeo community platform (<https://pangeo.io/>). This use case also aims to enhance data discovery and data access, relying on existing services provided by the Earth Sciences communities such as the Research Infrastructure Data Terra (<https://www.data-terra.org/en/accueil/>) in France, and the consortium of Environment Research Infrastructures (ENVRI) (<https://envri.eu/>) and the ENES climate community (<https://is.enes.org>) in Europe.

The Data Science notebooks will enable cross-domain data processing, regardless of scientific themes or organizations. Indeed, this will allow to perform, for example:

- Cross-sources studies such as integration of satellite and in-situ observation;
- Multi or cross-disciplinary studies in "Earth Environment sciences" communities (Solid Earth / Atmosphere / Ocean / Continental surfaces such as volcanoes and earthquakes, river flow or sustainability and safety of the coastline, Climate, etc.)
- Cross-disciplinary studies with other communities, such as biosphere (carbon cycle, impact of changes on biodiversity, etc.) or human activities (soil artificialisation, etc.)

2. EOSCPillar4EarthScience VRE

2.1. Overview

In order to deliver an open, cloud-enabled computing environment, a Virtual Data Analysis Platform, named **EOSCPillar4EarthScience**¹ VRE (Virtual Research Environment), has been deployed on the EOOSC-Pillar Gateway², the working environment powered by D4Science Infrastructure³ designed to promote the collaboration among people involved in the EOOSC-Pillar project tasks.

Figure 1: EOSCPillar4EarthScience VRE on the EOOSC-Pillar Gateway

¹ <https://eosc-pillar.d4science.org/group/eoscpillar4earthscience>

² <https://eosc-pillar.d4science.org>

³ <https://www.d4science.org>

It is built on top IT services and resources proposed by national infrastructures and involves many relevant technologies for an efficient access to remote data. Among them:

- **cloud computing resources** from EOSC-Pillar Work Package 7 (*The infrastructure layer: delivering horizontal data storage and computing services, from national WP7 to transnational*);
- **OpenStack Object Storage** (a.k.a. Swift) service from EOSC-Pillar partners, to ease and fasten access from the processing environment to the distributed data repositories;
- **D4Science Virtual Research Environment** to run data science notebooks;
- **Software Heritage** solution from the dedicated EOSC-Pillar use case, for the archive and sustainability of the source code.

The proposed web-based processing environment aims at addressing needs coming from two types of user from the Earth Environment & Geosciences communities:

1. *Scientists*, who want to run ready-to-use data processing “Pangeo ecosystem-based” scripts on their temporal and geographical areas of interest;
2. *Data analysts*, who want to develop, test and run their own data processing “Pangeo ecosystem-based” scripts adapted to their needs.

In this way, users will be able to conduct cross-domain or cross-sources analysis on remote platforms and HPC, without downloading the data or running the analysis on their local computer. This allows addressing some practical issues related to large-scale multi-model data analysis, for example related to strong requirements in terms of computational and storage resources, data access, need for specific tools and libraries, etc.

More specifically, the EOSCPillar4EarthScience VRE provides users with a personal JupyterLab workspace, enabling the access to the PANGEO⁴ tools and the Data Science Notebooks developed by the UC’s partners. Each user can either adapt the ready-to-use Jupyter Notebooks provided by the EOSC-Pillar UC6.2 partners or develop new notebooks and run them on the datasets of interest.

2.2. Data sources and services

The proposed virtual research environment provides access to large, heterogeneous and distributed data from ocean and climate domains. Specifically:

- **Ocean datasets:**
 - **Argo data collection**⁵ of temperature, salinity and velocity measurements made by 3000 Argo free-drifting profiling floats in the first 2000m of the ocean.
 - **CORA CMEMS dataset**⁶ built from a collection of in-situ data, either profiles or time series. This gridded product provides values for temperature and salinity between 1990 and 2018.

⁴ <https://pangeo.io>

⁵ <https://www.odatis-ocean.fr/en/data-and-services/data-access/direct-access-to-the-data-catalogue#/metadata/3df904de-e47d-4bf9-85a0-7c0942aff8b6>

⁶ <https://sextant.ifremer.fr/Donnees/Catalogue#/metadata/7691f8b8-1193-4aef-8e7e-0d7a9c88c057>

- **SMOS gridded data**⁷ from SMOS satellite on ocean surface salinity from 2010 to 2019.
- **GSLH collection**⁸ of gridded multi-mission sea surface heights computed with respect to a twenty-year mean. Several variables are proposed (Sea Level Anomaly, Absolute Dynamic Topography, Geostrophic Velocities).
- **Climate datasets:**
 - **CMIP**⁹ (Coupled Model Intercomparison Project) collections from the ESGF¹⁰ (Earth System Grid Federation) data archive.
 - **CORDEX**¹¹ (Coordinated Regional Climate Downscaling Experiment) datasets produced by GERICS¹² and published via the ESGF.

In order to avoid copying data to the VRE, which requires time and storage resources, two data services have been tested to provide fast and efficient access to such datasets: an **iRODS**¹³ (Integrated Rule-Oriented Data System) instance deployed at Ifremer premises and an **OpenStack Swift**¹⁴ instance deployed at DKRZ premises¹⁵. In addition, the intake¹⁶ and intake-esm¹⁷ packages enables users to easily search and discover the available datasets. However, due to some security and compliance issues, the OpenStack Swift instance is the only data service implemented in the final version of the VRE. The marine data and a limited set of climate data exploited in the use case have been replicated on the VRE local dataspace.

All the datasets are described through the EOSC-Pillar Federated FAIR Data Space (F2DS)¹⁸, which is a unifying data space that aggregates and enriches datasets from a set of scattered repositories/data sources and communities with the aim to facilitate the steps ranging from data discovery up to re-use in accordance with the FAIR principles and practices. All these datasets are published and made available into the D4Science EOSC-Pillar Data Catalog¹⁹ (Figure 2) offering search and browse on top of the aggregated datasets as well as the possibility to implement and integrate specific "views" of the whole data space into the available Virtual Research Environments.

⁷ <https://www.odatis-ocean.fr/en/data-and-services/data-access/direct-access-to-the-data-catalogue#/metadata/0f02fc28-cb86-4c44-89f3-ee7df6177e7b>

⁸ <https://resources.marine.copernicus.eu/products>

⁹ <https://www.wcrp-climate.org/wgcm-cmip>

¹⁰ L. Cinquini, D. Crichton et al., "The earth system grid federation: An open infrastructure for access to distributed geospatial data," Future Generation Computer Systems, vol. 36, pp. 400–417, 2014.

¹¹ <https://cordex.org>

¹² Climate Service Center Germany: <https://www.climate-service-center.de/index.php/en>

¹³ <https://irods.org/>

¹⁴ <https://wiki.openstack.org/wiki/Swift>

¹⁵ <https://www.dkrz.de/up/systems/swift>

¹⁶ <https://intake.readthedocs.io/en/latest/index.html>

¹⁷ <https://intake-esm.readthedocs.io/en/stable/>

¹⁸ EOSC-Pillar FAIR Data Point, a REST API and Web Client for storing catalogs, datasets and distributions. <https://f2ds.eosc-pillar.eu/login>

¹⁹ EOSC-Pillar Data Catalog, an environment mainly conceived to host and operate the overall research data catalog resulting from the EOSC-Pillar project. <https://eosc-pillar.d4science.org/group/eoscpillarresdatactlg/catalogue>

Figure 2: Climate (on the right) and Ocean (on the left) datasets published into the EOSC-Pillar Data Catalog

In this way, users can easily discover and access the metadata of the datasets integrated into the EOSCPillar4EarthScience catalog instance²⁰ embedded into the VRE itself (Figure 3), thus having a focused access on a community-defined part of the whole F2DS.

Figure 3: Climate and Ocean datasets synchronized into the EOSCPillar4EarthScience Catalog

²⁰ <https://eosc-pillar.d4science.org/group/eoscpillar4earthscience/catalogue>

2.3. Data Science Software stack

The entry point to the EOSCPillar4EarthScience VRE is implemented through JupyterHub²¹, which represents a server for running a multi-user Jupyter-based environment. The JupyterHub server spawns single-user notebook servers with the enhanced JupyterLab²² computing environment, the next-generation user interface for Project Jupyter.

This environment contains a wide set of pre-configured science modules from the Python ecosystem - and in particular from the PANGEO community²³ - for running data manipulation, analysis and visualization. It also includes the Ophidia High-Performance Data Analytics framework²⁴ as a solution for scientific data management.

Figure 4: JupyterLab computing environment provided by the EOSCPillar4EarthScience VRE

Data Search & Discovery

- **intake**: a lightweight package for finding, investigating, loading and disseminating data.
- **intake-esm**: an intake plugin for parsing an Earth System Model (ESM) collection/catalog and loading the desired assets (netCDF files and/or Zarr stores).

intake

Intake is a Pangeo Python package that interfaces the user with the requested data. It provides transparent access to local or remote data, allowing the user to search and load multi-dimensional data without needing to know the data location, data format, etc.

²¹ <https://jupyter.org/hub>

²² <https://jupyterlab.readthedocs.io/en/stable/#>

²³ <https://repository.eosc-pillar.eu/index.php/s/oLas27XDRwscwww#pdfviewer>

²⁴ <https://ophidia.cmcc.it>

Multiple plugins are available to improve Intake's compliance with different data storages and formats (Zarr, Parquet, local or cloud data (GCS, S3, etc.). Plugin development is also possible to integrate more data sources.

```
intake_cat = intake.open_catalog("/home/jovyan/eosc-pillar-dataspace/EOSCPillar4EarthScience/intake_cat.gui")
```



```
name: gslh
container: xarray
plugin: ['zarr']
driver: ['zarr']
description: sea-surface altimetry data from The Copernicus Marine Environment
direct_access: forbid
user_parameters: []
metadata:
  url: http://marine.copernicus.eu/services-portfolio/access-to-products/?option=om_csw&view=details&product_id=SEALEVEL_GLOBAL_PHY_L4_REP_OBSERVATIONS_008_047
```

```
ddf = intake_cat.argo(year=[2010], month=range(1, 6)).to_dask()
```

Figure 5: Multi-selection of heterogeneous datasets from diverse data sources through Intake Catalog

intake-esm

The *intake-esm* package provides a tool to access big amounts of data, without having to worry about where it comes from. It aims to facilitate:

- the discovery of earth's climate and weather datasets,
- the ingestion of these datasets into xarray dataset containers.

Loading a catalog

The root of the *intake-esm* catalog is an ESM (Earth System Model) collection definition file, which is a JSON file used by *intake-esm* to establish a link to a database (CSV file) that contains the data assets locations and the associated metadata (experiment, model, variable, ...). You can load data from an ESM Catalog by providing the URL to valid ESM Catalog:

```
catalog_url = "/path/to/the/json/file"
col = intake.open_esm_datastore(catalog_url)
col
```

The collection definition file is created by the data administrators, so knowing where it is and loading it is enough to search and discover data through *intake-esm*.

Search and Discovery

The `search()` method allows the user to perform a query against the catalog using keyword arguments. The keyword argument names must be the names of the columns in the catalog (i.e. CMIP metadata fields). The search method returns a subset of the catalog with all the entries that match the provided query.

By default, the `search()` method looks for exact matches:

```
col_subset = col.search(
    source_id=["CMCC-CM2-HR4"],
    variable_id=["tasmin"],
    experiment_id=["historical"],
    table_id="day"
)
col_subset.df
```

However, with use of wildcards and/or regular expressions, we can find all items with a particular substring in a given column:

Find all datasets related to the ssp (Shared Socio-economic Pathways) scenarios:

```
col.search(experiment_id="ssp*").df
```

Find all entries whose variable name starts with `tas`

```
col.search(long_name="^tas").df
```

Loading datasets

To load data assets into xarray datasets, we need to use the `to_dataset_dict()` method, which returns a dictionary of aggregated xarray datasets.

```
dset_dict = cat.to_dataset_dict()
```

We can list all the datasets keys

```
[key for key in dset_dicts.keys()]
```

and then access a particular dataset:

```
ds = dset_dicts[<key_1>]
ds
```

Data Manipulation & Analysis

- **xarray**²⁵: a Python package that provides a toolkit for working with labeled multi-dimensional arrays of data.
- **pandas**²⁶: a fast, powerful, flexible and easy to use open source tool offering data structures and operations for manipulating numerical tables and time series.
- **NumPy**²⁷: offers comprehensive mathematical functions, linear algebra routines, and much more.
- **SciPy**²⁸: provides algorithms for optimization, integration, interpolation, eigenvalue problems, algebraic equations, differential equations, statistics and many other classes of problems.
- **Pangeo-pyinterp**²⁹: a Python library for optimized geo-referenced interpolation.
- **PyOphidia**³⁰: an open source Python library for interacting with the instance of the Ophidia framework running in each user environment. It allows a programmable integration of the Ophidia operators into more articulated and shareable Data Science applications.
- **Dask**³¹: a flexible parallel computing library for analytics designed to provide parallelism to the existing Python stack.

Data Visualization

- **matplotlib**³²: a comprehensive library for creating static, animated, and interactive visualizations in Python.
- **cartopy**³³: a Python package designed to create customized and publication quality maps and geospatial visualizations.
- **folium**³⁴: a Python package to visualize data on an interactive map.
- **hvPlot**³⁵: provides a high-level plotting API that supports panning, zooming, hovering, and clickable/selectable legends.

2.4. Data Science notebooks

Notebook documents are documents produced by the Jupyter Notebook App containing both computer code (e.g. python) and rich text elements (paragraph, equations, figures, links, etc...). Notebook documents are both human-readable documents containing the analysis description and the results (figures, tables, etc..) as well as executable documents which can be run to perform data analysis.

²⁵ <https://docs.xarray.dev/en/stable/>

²⁶ <https://pandas.pydata.org>

²⁷ <https://numpy.org>

²⁸ <https://scipy.org>

²⁹ <https://github.com/CNES/pangeo-pyinterp>

³⁰ <https://github.com/OphidiaBigData/PyOphidia>

³¹ <https://dask.org>

³² <https://matplotlib.org>

³³ <https://scitools.org.uk/cartopy/docs/latest/>

³⁴ <https://python-visualization.github.io/folium/>

³⁵ <https://hvplot.holoviz.org>

The EOSCPillar4EarthScience VRE provides a set of ready-to-use Jupyter notebooks showing how to exploit the PANGEO tools to conduct on-demand online analysis on different types of data.

Earth Observation Data Science Notebooks

- **argo_gslh_colocation_sea_level**: the notebook shows how to cross-analyze Sea Level Anomalies satellite data and pressure anomalies in situ data over an area of interest selected by the user;
- **cora_smos_colocation_salinity**: the notebook shows how to combine sea salinity parameters from different data sources (satellite data and in situ data) over a temporal and spatial selection.
- **gslh_analysis**: the notebook shows how to use gridded sea-surface altimetry data (GSLH) to explore a list of variables, coordinates and metadata, visually examine some of the data, and compute the mean sea level.

Figure 6: Earth Observation Data Science Notebook running on the EOSCPillar4EarthScience VRE

Climate Data Science Notebooks

- **temperature_threshold_analysis**: the notebook shows how to search and use the *historical* experiment or one of the *Shared Socioeconomic Pathway* (SSP) experiments from the CMIP* climate models, count the annual summer days for the year and area of interest and visualize the results online.

- **temperature_anomaly_analysis**: the notebook shows how to compare historical and SSP experiments from different CMIP* climate models, analyze the data and obtain the global mean temperature anomaly on a chosen time range.
- **pr_Rnnmm_index**: the notebook shows how to search and select the *precipitation* variable for a given model and experiment among the available CMIP* models and experiments, obtain the annual count of days when precipitation exceeds a given threshold on the year and area of interest and visualize the result online.
- **mean_temperature_and_ETR**: the notebook shows how to search and select the *temperature* variable for a given model and experiment among the available CMIP* models and experiments, calculate the air temperature average and the extreme air temperature range over the time range of interest and visualize the result online.
- **PyOphidia_analysis**: the notebook shows how to exploit the Ophidia framework and its Python bindings, PyOphidia, to implement and run some simple examples of climate data analysis.

Figure 7: Climate Data Science Notebook running on the EOSCPillar4EarthScience VRE

3. EOSCPillar4EarthScience VRE on the EOOSC-Pillar Gateway

This section explains how to access the **EOSCPillar4EarthScience VRE** instance deployed on the EOOSC-Pillar Gateway and get started with all the features made available in the **JupyterLab** environment.

3.1. Access the EOSCPillar4EarthScience VRE

- **Sign up for an account on the EOOSC-Pillar Gateway.** If you don't have an account yet, you can register here (<https://eosc-pillar.d4science.org/group/eoscpillar4earthscience>) using your institutional credentials or any other supported identity providers (Google, Twitter, GitHub, LinkedIn, etc.).

The screenshot shows the login interface for the EOOSC-Pillar Gateway. It includes a header with the 'EOOSC-Pillar GATEWAY' logo and the 'D4SCIENCE INFRASTRUCTURE' logo. The main content area is titled 'Log In' and contains a form with the following elements:

- Username or email:** A text input field.
- Password:** A password input field.
- Remember me:** A checkbox.
- Forgot Password?:** A link.
- Log In:** A blue button.
- Social Login Options:** A vertical list of buttons for 'Academic / other', 'LinkedIn', 'Google', 'Twitter', and 'GitHub'.
- Registration Link:** A link for 'New user? Register'.
- Footer:** Links for 'Terms of Use', 'Cookies Policy', 'Privacy Policy', and 'Project Home'. A notice states: 'EOOSC Pillar has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 857650. The views and opinions expressed in this publication are the sole responsibility of the author and do not necessarily reflect the views of the European Commission.' The European Union flag is also present.

Figure 8: Registration on the EOOSC-Pillar Gateway

- **Join the EOSCPillar4EarthScience VRE.** The membership policy for the EOSCPillar4EarthScience VRE is “restricted”, so any membership request has to be approved by the VRE Managers. After your account is registered, visit the following link (<https://eosc-pillar.d4science.org/group/eosc-pillar-gateway/explore>) to see all the EOOSC-Pillar services and working environments developed by research communities

to help build an Open Science and FAIR data-based EOSC. Among them, find the service called “EOSCPILLAR4EarthScience VRE”, click on “Request Access” and “Confirm request” to send your request to the D4Science VRE moderators.

Figure 9: Registration to the EOSCPillar4EarthScience VRE

- Once a D4Science VRE moderator has approved your request, you will receive a confirmation email containing a link to connect to the VRE. The D4Science4EarthScience VRE is now listed in the EOSC-Pillar Gateway page (<https://eosc-pillar.d4science.org/group/eosc-pillar-gateway>), under both the “My Working Environment” and “Use Case Environments” sections.

Figure 10: EOSC-Pillar Gateway homepage

3.2. Access the JupyterLab environment and the Jupyter notebooks

Access the EOSCPillar4EarthScience VRE (<https://eoscpillar.d4science.org/group/eoscpillar4earthscience>) and click on “Jupyter” under “Analytics” in the upside bar menu to choose the server options and start your JupyterLab environment.

Figure 11: EOSCPillar4EarthScience VRE on the EOSC-Pillar Gateway

As you can see from the image below, there are three different configurations - **Default Small**, **Medium** and **Large** - which differ in terms of CPU and RAM allocated. To avoid the allocation of unneeded resources, three more server profiles - **Ophidia Small**, **Medium** and **Large** - are available to spawn a Notebook server including the Ophidia back-end support.

Figure 12: Notebook server options

The user environment is organized around two main directories: **workspace** and **eosc-pillar-dataspac**.

The **workspace** directory is a special folder corresponding to the overall user workspace that is seamlessly shared across several applications and services, including *EOSCPillar4EarthScience*.

The **eosc-pillar-dataspac** directory hosts a limited set of **data** (`/home/jovyan/eosc-pillar-dataspac/EOSCPillar4EarthScience/RO/data` and `/home/jovyan/eosc-pillar-dataspac/EOSCPillar4EarthScience/RW`) made locally available to enable data analytics use cases that rely on tools and libraries not fully compliant with the underlying data services. It also includes the ready-to-use **notebooks** (`/home/jovyan/eosc-pillar-dataspac/EOSCPillar4EarthScience/RO/notebooks`) implemented by UC6.2 and shared among all the users (in read-only mode) and the YAML files (`/home/jovyan/eosc-pillar-dataspac/EOSCPillar4EarthScience/RO/intake`) used to describe the **intake** catalogs associated with the local datasets.

Figure 13: EOSCPillar4EarthScience VRE ready-to-use notebooks

3.3. Available kernels

A notebook *kernel* is a “computational engine” that executes the code contained in a Notebook document. The default notebook server includes a Python kernel (**Python 3** or **Python [conda env:root]**) with a number of preinstalled community libraries. When you open a Notebook document, the associated kernel is automatically launched. When the notebook is executed (either cell-by-cell or from the menu Run → Run All Cells), the kernel performs the computation and produces the results.

Figure 14: EOSCPillar4EarthScience VRE notebook kernels

In addition to the default kernel, two dedicated environments, **conda env:dataterra** and **conda env:climate**, are provided to overcome possible package versioning issues when running some Earth Observation and Climate Data Science Notebooks, respectively. You can easily change the notebook kernel from the menu: Kernel → Change Kernel.

3.4. Run a Jupyter Notebook

The content of the *workspace* folder has to be managed with care since it is not locally available on the JupyterLab instance you are using. It is recommended to create local copies

of the files you are willing to work with (i.e. to have the files you are working with available in place other than on the workspace folder) and then copy them back into the workspace (when your working session is going to be closed), thus making the changes available for future uses. Therefore, we recommend creating a personal folder under the “/” folder (**/home/jovyan**) where you’ll be able to copy, modify, create and run any notebook without any interference. For example, after testing a ready-to-use notebook located under the *eosc-pillar-dataspace* folder (`/home/jovyan/eosc-pillar-dataspace/EOSCPillar4EarthScience/RO/notebooks`), you may want to use it as a starting point to implement a new notebook by yourself. To do this, you can simply copy the read-only notebook under your personal folder and start playing with the available data, modules and tools. Any notebook, file and folder stored under the root folder (`/home/jovyan`) is persistent, so always available at each new session.

Figure 15: EOSCPillar4EarthScience VRE notebook execution

Glossary

API	Application Programming Interface
CMEMS	Copernicus Marine Environment Monitoring Service
CMIP	Coupled Model Intercomparison Project
CORA	Coriolis Ocean database ReAnalysis
CORDEX	Coordinated Regional Climate Downscaling Experiment
CSV	Comma-separated values
ENES	European Network for Earth System Modelling
ENVRI	Environment Research Infrastructures
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ESGF	Earth System Grid Federation
ESM	Earth System Model
F2DS	Federated FAIR Data Space
FAIR	Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, Reusability
GCS	Google Cloud Storage
HPC	High Performance Computing
iRODS	Integrated Rule-Oriented Data System
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
NetCDF	Network Common Data Form
S3	Simple Storage Service
SMOS	Soil Moisture and Ocean Salinity
SSP	Shared Socioeconomic Pathway
VRE	Virtual Research Environment

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